

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES AND WEAR CHARACTERISTICS OF BACTERIAL CELLULOSE / POLYMER COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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SUMMARY

The mechanical properties and wear characteristics of Bacterial Cellulose (BC) composites are investigated. Fabrication method of BC form, in which BC microfibril network of three dimensional nano-structure and their bonding conditions remains, was developed and the characteristics of BC form and its applicability to impregnation of polymer resin were considered.

Keywords: Composite Materials, Bacterial Cellulose, 3D Nano-Structure, Wear, Mechanical Property, Fabrication Method.

1 INTRODUCTION

Bacterial Cellulose (BC) is one of the eco-friendly materials, and is synthesized by the acetic bacterium *Acetobacter xylinum* [1-5]. The fibrous structure of BC consists of three-dimensional network of microfibrils containing glucan chains bound together by hydrogen bond [6].

The authors have developed fabrication method for Bacterial Cellulose (BC) composite materials of sheet type [7]. In the cases of CaCO₃/BC composites and Clay/BC composites, it is found that the BC composites have a maximum value of Young's modulus at an optimum value of reinforcement contents. BC composite materials could be effectively used as the high performance structural components for various applications [8, 9]. In order to reinforce composite materials with BC, the effective processing method is required for keeping the effective hydrogen bond between the BC and fillers, and physical entanglement of three-dimensionally oriented BC microfibril networks of nano-scale [5, 6].

In this paper, the fabrication method and mechanical properties of Bacterial Cellulose (BC) Form / Polymer composites are investigated. A fabrication method of BC form, in which BC microfibril network of three dimensional structure and their bonding conditions remain, is developed, and the characteristics of BC form and its applicability to impregnation of polymer resin are considered in order to apply to the high performance structural components, for example, a robot-hand system of humanoid robots. Wear tests for the BC Form / Polymer composites are conducted under dry sliding condition. The effects of material properties and configurations on the properties of BC composites are discussed, and three dimensional micro structure for strengthening in BC composites is also considered.

2 FABRICATION METHOD AND CHARACTERISTICS OF BC FORM

Let us develop a fabrication method of BC form, and consider characteristics of BC form and its applicability to impregnation of polymer resin.

2.1. Fabrication Method of Bacterial Cellulose Forms

The material used in this study is Bacterial Cellulose (BC) which was industrial waste provided by Japanese traditional vinegar maker. The polymerization of BC is about 3000 and its contents of nitrogen is about 0.2 - 0.4% [6]. The added reinforcements of BC composite are powdered paper (PP), calcium carbonate (CaCO_3), and clay (Montmorillonite).

Using a mixer, the BC slurry was mixed with a small amount of water and broken into fine pieces. Adding reinforcements into it, the slurry was blended well into a source of BC mixture. After pouring the BC slurry into a container of cup type, it was frozen in a freezer. Frozen samples were dehydrated in a vacuum chamber, and then we had BC forms in which three-dimensional network of BC microfibrils and their bonding conditions remain. Specific volume of 3D-BC forms developed was $100 - 200\text{cm}^3/\text{g}$. Figure 1 shows scanning electron microscope (SEM) photographs for surfaces of BC form.

(a) Surface of BC form

(b) Observation in high magnification view ($\times 7000$)

Figure 1 SEM observations for surfaces of BC form.

2.2. Characteristics of BC Forms

It is easily found from the photographs that there is a three-dimensional microfibril network in the BC form, and thin BC sheets of several micrometer thickness are layered and making a unit cell of stacked BC sheets with hundred micrometer order. In observation at high magnification, BC microfibrils of nano-scale are randomly entangled with each other, CaCO_3 fillers are well dispersed in three-dimensional network of BC microfibrils. This BC network with reinforcement fillers could give the high Young's modulus of BC composite materials.

X-ray CT examination for BC form specimens was performed in order to evaluate the homogeneity of BC form. Figure 2 shows x-ray photographs of CaCO_3/BC composite form of 50mm diameter and 30mm thickness. Figure 2(a) shows a scanning picture of horizontal cross section of BC form, and the photographs of Figure 2(b) and 2(c) are images of vertical cross section along two lines indicated in Figure 2(a).

White parts in pictures correspond to BC and black parts are air cavities. Larger cavities are observed in the middle part of BC form because it takes long time to freeze the water of BC slurry in the middle central part due to heat conduction and the low growing speed of ice causes the different size of ice which yields the different cell size of BC microfibril network.

This consideration is schematically shown in Figure 3. At the first stage, BC microfibrils dispersed homogeneously in large amount of water. In the next stage of freezing process, BC fibrils were put away by frozen ice crystals and gathered up with each other around the surface of ice crystals to make BC microfibril network of cell structure. By holding the BC form in a vacuum chamber, the water would be sublimed from the frozen BC slurry, and finally the dried BC form with complicated geometry of microfibril network could be obtained.

Figure 2 X-ray CT examination for BC form.

Figure 3 BC form after fabrication process.

3 EXAMINATION OF 3D-BC FORM / POLYMER COMPOSITES

We examined some types of a combination of 3D-BC form / polymer composite material. The characteristics of 3D-BC form / epoxy resin composites and 3D-BC form / phenol resin composites are reported in this study.

3.1. Examination 3D-BC Form / Polymer Composites

Let us examine the characteristics of 3D-BC form by processing it with the epoxy resin. Figure 4 shows SEM photographs of fracture surfaces of 3D-BC form / epoxy resin composite material which was broken in the liquid nitrogen. Figure 1(a) and Figure 4(a) were taken at same magnification power for fracture surface observation. Seeing the photograph of fracture surface of Figure 4(a), the material consists of BC unit cells in contact with each other. It is found from Figure 4(b) at high magnification that the epoxy resin was fully impregnated into complicated structure of BC cell. Some interlaminar debondings between BC cells were observed in the parts of fracture surface. It remains unclear at the present time that the interlaminar debondings occurred in impregnation process of resin or in the fracture process in liquid nitrogen.

(a) Surface of BC form

(b) Observation in high magnification

Figure 4 SEM photographs of fracture surfaces of 3D-BC form / Epoxy resin composites.

3.2. Wear Characteristics of 3D-BC Form / Phenol resin Composites

We also examined another combination of 3D-BC form/Polymer composite material. By using the BC form with water contents, the phenol resin penetrated into the BC form and the drying process was taken for the water in the BC form at the same time. The method developed by two of the authors is called the Direct Impregnation Method (DIM) [10]. After taking this procedure, the mixture was dried and hardened in order to get the BC FRP pre-impregnation (BC p/p) of desired shape. In the next stage, BC p/p was processed into the B stage, pressed at 433K (160°C) and with 1MPa, and then we had transparent BC FRP plates of brown colour. In Figure 5, it is found that the composite has the characteristic of transparency before carbonizing process.

The BC FRP plates were burned out in the inactive gas environment at 1373K (1100°C) and the heating rate 5K/hr, and finally we had a carbonized BC form / Phenol resin composite materials, that is, “nano-C/C composites”. By burning BC FRP p/p at 1373K, BC microfibrils were changed into the carbon fibres of nano-scale, and the phenol resin of the matrix became the glassy carbon. It means that the composite is a kind of carbon / carbon composites. The diameter of BC microfibrils is about 10nm.

Figure 5 Photograph of 3D-BC form / Phenol resin composites.

(a) Schematic view

(b) Close-up of testing apparatus

Figure 6 Pin-on-drum type tribology tester.

In order to examine the properties of the nano-C/C composites, the wear tests were conducted by using the pin-on-drum type tribology tester shown Figure 6. The specimen of 3.5mm×3.5mm square was sliding on surface of SUS304 drum of the surface roughness Ra 0.3-0.5. The sliding conditions were as follows; sliding speed 1.5m/sec, sliding distance 130km, and contact pressure 1MPa.

According to wear tests, the carbonized BC FRP composites have sufficiently low coefficient of friction and significant low factor of wear. The coefficient of wear took the low values of 0.17-0.18 during the tests. The specific factor of wear element loss for the carbonized BC FRP is $3.77 \times 10^{-10} \text{ mm}^2/\text{N}$. The factor is given by the equation;

$$\text{Specific factor of wear element loss} [\text{mm}^2/\text{N}] = \frac{\text{Volume of wear} [\text{mm}^3]}{\text{Load} [\text{N}] \times \text{Sliding distance} [\text{mm}]} \quad (1)$$

In the comparison with the value of $5 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mm}^2/\text{N}$ for silicon nitride (Si_3N_4) ceramics and $4 \times 10^{-8} \text{ mm}^2/\text{N}$ for Diamond-Like Carbon (DLC), it reveals that the carbonized BC FRP composites have more excellent wear property than Si_3N_4 ceramics and the DLC. For your reference, the specific factor for steels is with the order of 10^{-2} and that for carbon materials with the order of 10^{-6} .

Figure 7 shows the SEM photographs for observing the surface of the carbonized BC FRP composites before wear tests. It can be seen from the photographs that many BC microfibrils of nano-scale are dispersed over the cross section of the composites, aligned along the vertical to the surface or the parallel to it. Some BC bundles of micrometer diameter are observed in the photos.

After wear tests, we examined the sliding surface of the carbonized BC FRP composites. SEM observation for the sliding surfaces of nano-C/C composites are shown in Figure 8. Figure 9 shows photographs for the surfaces of the composites by using Atomic Force Microscope (AFM). From the Figure 8, a crack of some hundred nm length occurred at the sliding surface, propagating into the inside and then a small piece of the material were dropped off. According to AFM observation, it is easily found that many ends of BC microfibrils appear on the sliding surface. In nano-C/C composites, many carbonized BC microfibril of nano-scale were dispersed in glassy carbon made from the matrix of phenol resin. When the wear element loses by sliding force in tests, the fracture pass was affected by nano-scale BC microfibrils, and a large energy was absorbed during micro crack propagation. The composites has high fracture toughness and good wear characteristic, and this constituent contributes to very low value of the specific factor of wear element loss and the coefficient of wear.

The BC microfibrils, which were combined together with the matrix of polymer, worked and had some effect on the higher value of the fracture toughness of BC composites, and then the specific wear rate becomes higher in wear tests. It is found that the BC nano-fibres their selves and the interface bonding condition between nano-fibres and the matrix play an important role for wear characteristic of materials, and many applications of the BC composites could be expected for the mechanical elements of machines.

Figure 7 Cross section of nano-C/C composites before wear tests.

Figure 8 SEM observation for sliding surfaces of nano-C/C composites.

Figure 9 AFM observation for sliding surfaces of nano-C / C composites.

4 CONCLUDING REMARKS

In this paper, the fabrication method and mechanical properties of Bacterial Cellulose (BC) Form / Polymer composites were investigated. The effects of material properties and configurations on the properties of BC composites were discussed, and three dimensional micro structure for strengthening in BC composites was also considered.

- (1) A fabrication method of BC form, in which BC microfibril network of three dimensional structure and their bonding conditions remain, was developed and the characteristics of BC form and its applicability to impregnation of polymer resin were considered in order to apply to the high performance structural components.
- (2) The characteristics of 3D-BC form were examined by processing it with the epoxy resin. It is found that the epoxy resin was impregnated well into complicated structure of BC cell.
- (3) The experimental results of wear characteristics were shown for the BC Form / Phenol resin composites. Wear tests of the BC composites were conducted under dry sliding condition. The coefficient of wear took the low values of 0.17-0.18 during the tests. The specific factor of wear element loss for the carbonized BC FRP was $3.77 \times 10^{-10} \text{ mm}^2/\text{N}$. It reveals that the BC composites have excellent wear property in comparison with silicon nitride ceramics and the diamond-like carbon. The BC microfibrils, which were combined together with the matrix of polymer, worked and had some effect on the higher value of the fracture toughness of BC composites, and then the specific wear rate becomes higher in wear tests.

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